

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.613 Max: 62.773	1452 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1473-1478 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *Tufo floor surface adjacent to cut 1451*

Covered by	Fills	Filled by
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1417	<input type="checkbox"/> SU:	<input type="checkbox"/> SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
			Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

NOT EXCAVATED IN 2011

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1453	Abuts: 1478
Is covered by: 1417	Covers:
Is cut by: 1451	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

Remnant tufo floor surface, small patch that has been cut

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *South-western portion of house, Northern section of Room #6.*

Shape: *Rectangular with a slightly diagonal southern limit.*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight</p> <p>Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) *crushed tufo floor*

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

*110 cm long, 78 cm at
 Description: widest point.
 Small, almost rectangular
 patch of tufo surface in
 the northern section of
 room # 6, roughly
 preserved.*

INTERPRETATION

*Possible floor layer beneath tufo floor su 1417.
 Older tufo floor, maybe the oldest floor surface*

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<i>AKR AMB</i>	on	<i>26/7/2011</i>
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